

INGLIZ TILIDA HOZIRGI ZAMON MODAL FE'LLAR NAZARIYASI

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Hozirgi zamon ingliz tilidagi modal fe'llar nazariy va amaliy jihatdan, shuningdek sintaktik-semantik jihatdan har tomonlama o'rganib chiqishdir. Ushbu maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun quyidagilar vazifalarni hal qilishni o'z oldimizga qo'ydik:

1. Hozirgi zamon ingliz tilida "can" va "to able to" borasidagi ishlarni ko'rib chiqish va ularga munosabat bildirish;
2. Mavjud nuqtai-nazarlarga ijodiy yondoshib, ularning nazariy va amaliy ma'nolarini o'rganish;
3. "to have to" larni "must" modal fe'li mustaqil va yordamchi fe'llar bilan qiyoslab o'rganish asosida ularning struktura bo'yicha tavsiyalar berish;
4. Gap qurilishida modal fe'llarning roli va o'rnini aniqlash;
5. Zamonaviy ingliz va Amerikalik yozuvchilarning badiiy asarlaridan olingan misollardan foydalanib modal fe'llarning sintaktik va semantic xususiyatlarini atroflicha o'rganib chiqish.

Ilmiy ishning metodologik asosi shundan iboratki, bu yerda modal fe'llarning bir-biri bilan qiyoslab, taqqoslab o'rganish bo'lsa, tadqiq usuli hozirgi zamonaviy ingliz tilida va asosan Amerika ingliz tilisida modal fe'llarning atroflicha qisqartirishlar orqali ishlatilayotganini bayon qilishdir. Tahlil qilish orqali uning turli leksik ma'nolarini aniqlash va bu oborotlar qatnashgan gaplarni tarjima qilganda ularning o'zbek tilidagi muqobil variantlarini topish tadqiqotning ilmiyligidir. Mazkur ilmiy ishning amaliy ahamiyati Ingliz tilining nazariy va amaliy grammatikasi fanlari uchun berilgan materiallar ilmiy qiymatga ega bo'lib, ulardan modal fe'llarning turli yo'nalishda misol uchun: she'r, hikoya, asar, informativ mavzusida ilmiy maqolalar yozishda, ingliz tili grammatikasidan shu mavzuda amaliy mashg'ulotlar o'tishda foydalanish mumkin.

Ko'pgina modal fe'llar (can/could/should/may/might/must/need/ought to) bilan ham majhul nisbat hosil qilish mumkin.

1. Hozirgi zamonda yuqoridagi modal fe'llardan keyin be + V3(ed) shaklini keltirish yo'li bilan majhul nisbat hosil qilinadi.

You must clean the room. (active voice) → The room must be cleaned. (passive voice)

Somebody may break the window. (active voice) → The window may be broken. (passive voice)

2. O'tgan zamonda yuqoridagi modal fe'llardan keyin have been + V3(ed) shaklini keltirish yo'li bilan majhul nisbat hosil qilinadi.

The room looks nice. You must have cleaned it. (active voice) → The room must have been cleaned. (passive voice)

Somebody may have broken the window. (active voice) → The window may have been broken. (passive voice)

Bu ilmiy ishning yangiligi shundaki unda nafaqat ehtimollik, zaruriyatni balki zamonaviy ingliz tilida ayniqsa og'zaki tilda hozirgi Amerika Ingliz tilida modal fe'llarning qisqartmalar yoki lahjalarga moslashtirib aytilishini yoritib berildi. Modal fe'llarning har birining o'zida tub ma'no yotib qaysi birini qay paytda qo'llay bilish ularni o'rganish, bir-biri bilan joyini almashtirmaslik haqida ham keng yoritilib bergan.

Majhul nisbat qurilmasi bilan axborot berish:

Tasdiqlanmagan xabarlar (mish-mish) yoki rasmiy yangiliklar haqida majhul nisbat qurilmasi to be +V3(ed) orqali ma'lumot berishimiz mumkin. Bunday gaplar it is said that..., it is reported that... so'zlari bilan boshlanadi.

It is said that George has been married six times. (Aytishlaricha, Jorj olti marta uylanganmish.)

It is believed that the Earth is the only planet to support life. (Ishoniladiki, yer hayot mavjud bo'lgan yagona planetadir.)

It is reported that two people were arrested by the police. (Xabar berilishicha, ikki nafar shaxs politsiya tomonidan hibsga olingan)

Quyidagi fe'llar ham axborot/xabar berish maqsadida majhul nisbat qurilmasida kela oladi. (to be) thought - o'ylashlaricha alleged - gumon qilinishicha understood - tushunishlaricha considered - o'ylashlaricha supposed - taxmin qilinishicha

It is alleged that he kicked the policeman → He is alleged to have kicked the policeman.

▪ Yuqoridagi qoidalarga qo'shimcha tarzda ma'lumot berish uchun There + majhul nisbat qurilmasi ning qo'llanishi mumkinligini aytib o'tish lozim.

There are believed to be thousands of homeless teenagers living on the streets of the capital.

▪ Xabar yoki axborot berish ma'nosidan tashqari to be supposed to iborasi boshqa ma'noda ham qo'llanadi.

Qiyoslash uchun:

George is supposed to have six wives. (Jorjning oltita xotini bor emish.)

You are supposed to eat more vegetables. (Siz ko'proq sabzavotlardan tanovul qilishingiz kerak.)

Modal fe'llarning ekvivalentlari o'rtasida alohida o'rin tutadigan "Can", "Could", "To be able to", "Need", "May", "Might", "Must", "Should", "to have to" tadqiqotning ob'yektidir. Kaushanskaya quyidagicha to'xtalib o'tadi: "Modal verbs are used to show the speaker's attitude toward the action or state indicated by the infinitive, I, e, they show that the action indicated by the infinitive is considered as possible, impossible, probable, improbable, obligatory, necessary, advisable, doubtful or uncertain, etc. The modal verbs are: can (could), may (might), must, should, ought, shall, will, would, need, dare. The modal expressions to be+infinitive and to have+infinitive also belong here". "Modal verbs are called defective because all of them (except "dare" and need) lack verbals and analytical forms" (i.e. compound tenses, analytical forms of the subjunctive Mood, the Passive

Voice)”. J. Bo’ronov o’zining “Ingliz tili grammatikasi” darslik kitobida modal fe’llarning qo’yidagi xususiyatlariga ham alohida to’xtalib o’tadi: uning fikricha modal fe’llardan sifatdosh formasini yasab bo’lmaydi. Suffiks yoki prefikslar yordamida modal fe’llardan yangi fe’llar yasalmaydi, chunki modal fe’llarning o’zlari so’z yasash usuli yordamida boshqa so’zlardan yasalgan emas. Modal fe’llar to yuklamasini olmasligining sababi, preterit-prezent fe’llarning infinitiv formasidan emas, balki hozirgi zamon formasidan yasaladi. Anglatgan ma’nosiga ko’ra majburiylik, mumkinlik, zarurlik, ishonch, hohish yoki ruxsat, taxmin, faraz qilish, qo’lidan kelishlik va shunga o’xshash boshqa ma’nolarni ifodalovchi fe’llar modal fe’llar deyiladi. Modal fe’llar harakatni ko’rsatmasligi tufayli boshqa fe’llardan semantic jihatdan farq qiladi.

Modal fe’llar doimo infinitive shaklidagi asosiy fe’llar bilan birga ishlatilib asosiy fe’llarga modallik ma’nosini qo’shadi. Gordon modal fe’llarga quyidagicha ta’rif beradi: “Modal verbs are defective verbs since they each many forms a modal compound predicate. They lack –s in the third person singular in the Present tense and have no verbals, so they have no analytical forms, some of them lack the form of the Past tense”. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo’lsak, modal fe’llarni o’qitish bugungi kun nuqtayi nazardan ahamiyatli hisoblanadi. Shu sababdan bugungi ilmiy ishimizda modal fe’llarni ilmiy yoritishga harakat qildik.

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